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Poor Families Burdened by Housing Costs in Europe

Between 2010 and 2021 they decreased by 19.01% on average for the countries considered

The Eurostat calculates an indicator that measures the share of the population that lives in families who spend 40% or more of their income available for the house net of the accommodation allowances. The costs of homes include payments of rented interest or mortgage including the cost of public services such as water, electricity, gas, or heating.

Ranking of European countries by the value of the presence of poor families burdened by the cost of the home in 2021. Greece is in the first place for the value of the presence of poor families burdened by the cost of the home in 2021 with an amount of 28.8%, followed by Denmark with an amount of 15.5% and Switzerland with an amount of 14.8%. In the middle of the standings there are the Czech Republic with an amount of 6.2%, followed by Austria with a value of 6.1% and Portugal with an amount of 5.9%. Ireland, Cyprus, and Hungary close the ranking with a value equal to 2.5%.

Ranking of countries by the value of the percentage variation of the presence of poor families burdened by the cost of the home between 2010 and 2021. Bulgaria is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the presence of poor families burdened by the cost of the home between the 2010 and 2021 with an amount of 96.61% or equal to an amount of 5.70 units, followed by Greece with an amount of 59.12% equal to a value of 10.70 units and from Portugal with an amount of 40.48% equal to an amount of 1.70 units. In the middle of the ranking there are Belgium with a variation of -15.73% equal to an amount of -1.40 units, followed by Austria with an amount of -18.67% equal to a value of -1.40 Unit and from Cyprus with a value of -19.35% equal to an amount of 0.60 units. Croatia closes the ranking with an amount of -68.09% equal to an amount of 9.60 units, followed by Lithuania with an amount of -74.53% equal to an amount of -7.90 units and by Hungary With an amount of -77.88% equal to an amount of -8.80 units. On average in the period considered the percentage of poor families burdened by the cost of the home has decreased from a value of 9.44% up to a value of 7.65% or equal to an amount of -19.01% equal to an amount of -1,79 units.

Changes in the percentage of families burdened by the cost of homes between 2020 and 2021. However, if we take into consideration the period between 2020 and 2021 it is possible to verify that there are 13 countries for which the percentage of poor families burdened by the cost of Housing has grown. These countries are: Netherlands with +50.60%, Portugal with +43.90%, Cyprus with 31.58%, Germany +22.22%, Spain with +20.73%. Poland with +16.33%, Denmark with +9.93%, Switzerland with +8.82%, Croatia with +7.14%, Romania with +5.63%, Finland with 4.88%, Sweden with 2.41%, Latvia with +2.08%. It should be considered that in these countries the population may have suffered more for the negative economic consequences of Covid 19. However, there are also countries for which between 2020 and 2021 the value of the percentage of poor families burdened by housing costs have decreased That is Austria with -3.18%, Malta with -3.57%, Belgium with -3.85%,

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Czech Republic with -4.62%, Slovenia with -6.82%, Greece with -13.51%, Bulgaria with -19.44%, Luxembourg with -40.00%, Ireland with -44.44%, Hungary with -48.98%.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below is a clusterization with the K-means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The analysis shows the presence of three different clusters or:

- Cluster 1: Slovenia, Estonia, Ireland, Finland, Austria, Portugal, Cyprus, Malta, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Croatia, Poland, Italy, Sweden, Latvia, Czech Republic, Belgium, Spain;
- Cluster 2: Germany, Denmark, Romania, Netherlands, Bulgaria, Switzerland, Hungary;
- Cluster 3: Greece.

From the median point of view, it appears that the value of the C3 is dominant compared to the C2 and C1. Specifically, there is the following system or $C3 = 28.8 > C2 = 11.6 > C1 = 5$. From a geographical point of view, it appears that Greece is the first country by the value of poor families burdened by housing costs, followed by a mix of countries also with high income including Germany and the Netherlands, and followed by the set of other European countries. The data relating to France are not reported due to missing values.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A network analysis is presented below with the use of the Euclidean distance. Two structures are identified with complex networks and three structures with simplified networks. There is the following complex network structure between the following countries or:

- Slovenia has a connection with Ireland for an amount equal to 0.39 units and with Finland with an amount of 0.28 units;
- Ireland has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.39 units and with Finland equal to an amount of 0.39 units;
- Finland has a connection with Slovenia for an amount of 0.28 units and with Ireland for an amount of 0.39 units.

There is also a complex network structure between the following countries or:

- The Czech Republic has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.36 units, and with Belgium for an amount of 0.42 units;
- Belgium has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.42 units and with Spain for an amount of 0.21 units;
- Spain has a connection with the Czech Republic for an amount of 0.36 and with Belgium for an amount of 0.21 units.

In addition, there are three different structures with simplified networks or:

- Latvia has a connection with Poland for an amount of 0.4 units;
- Italy has a connection with Sweden equal to an amount of 0.22 units;
- Malta and Cyprus have a connection for a value of 0.44 units.

Conclusions. The data show the presence of a decreasing trend between 2010 and 2021 of the value of poor families who are burdened by housing costs. However, in 2021 about 7.65% of European families were burdened by excess housing costs. Considering the set of economic crises, recession, inflation, growth in energy prices, it is very likely that in the absence of adequate economic policy

interventions, the percentage of families burdened by housing costs could grow in the future. In this regard, European policy makers must also intervene with economic policies in support of income and for the promotion of the distribution of real estate property at the population of European families.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

Ranking dei paesi per presenza di famiglie povere gravate dal costo dell'abitazione nel 2021.

Rank	Country	2021	Rank	Country	2021
1	<i>Greece</i>	28,8	14	<i>Portugal</i>	5,9
2	<i>Denmark</i>	15,5	15	<i>Poland</i>	5,7
3	<i>Switzerland</i>	14,8	16	<i>Luxembourg</i>	5,1
4	<i>Netherlands</i>	12,5	17	<i>Latvia</i>	4,9
5	<i>Bulgaria</i>	11,6	18	<i>Croatia</i>	4,5
6	<i>Germany</i>	11	19	<i>Estonia</i>	4,4
7	<i>Spain</i>	9,9	20	<i>Finland</i>	4,3
8	<i>Sweden</i>	8,5	21	<i>Slovenia</i>	4,1
9	<i>Belgium</i>	7,5	22	<i>Lithuania</i>	2,7
10	<i>Romania</i>	7,5	23	<i>Malta</i>	2,7
11	<i>Italy</i>	7,2	24	<i>Ireland</i>	2,5
12	<i>Czechia</i>	6,2	25	<i>Cyprus</i>	2,5
13	<i>Austria</i>	6,1	26	<i>Hungary</i>	2,5

Ranking dei paesi per variazione percentuale delle famiglie povere gravate dal costo dell'abitazione tra il 2010 ed il 2021.

Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per	Rank	Country	Var Ass	Var Per
1	Bulgaria	5,70	96,61	14	Cyprus	-0,60	-19,35
2	Greece	10,70	59,12	15	Germany	-3,50	-24,14
3	Portugal	1,70	40,48	16	Estonia	-1,60	-26,67
4	Sweden	0,70	8,97	17	Malta	-1,00	-27,03
5	Luxembourg	0,40	8,51	18	Denmark	-6,40	-29,22
6	Switzerland	0,70	4,96	19	Czechia	-3,50	-36,08
7	Finland	0,10	2,38	20	Poland	-3,40	-37,36
8	Spain	0,20	2,06	21	Ireland	-2,40	-48,98
9	Slovenia	-0,20	-4,65	22	Latvia	-4,90	-50,00
10	Italy	-0,50	-6,49	23	Romania	-8,30	-52,53
11	Netherlands	-1,50	-10,71	24	Croatia	-9,60	-68,09
12	Belgium	-1,40	-15,73	25	Lithuania	-7,90	-74,53
13	Austria	-1,40	-18,67	26	Hungary	-8,80	-77,88